

STUDY OF THE ASSORTMENT POLICY AT THE JOINT VENTURE LLC "SIYOB SAHOVATI"

Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna

Assistant professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7050247>

Abstract. This article discusses the volume of production and assortment policy, analysis of the range of products, dependence on external partners, as well as a systematic analysis of market conditions.

Keywords: enterprises, association, modernization, analysis, assortment policy, export, vegetables, fruits.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АССОРТИМЕНТНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ НА СП ООО «СИЁБ САХОВАТИ»

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются объемы производства и ассортиментная политика, анализ ассортимента продукции, зависимость от внешних партнеров, а также системный анализ конъюнктуры рынка.

Ключевые слова: предприятия, объединение, модернизация, анализ, ассортиментная политика, экспорт, овощи, фрукты.

INTRODUCTION

OOOSP "Siyob Sakhovati" is one of the leading enterprises in the Association "Uzbekozikovkatholding" and in accordance with the state program for the modernization of production enterprises in the period from 2012 to the present day, the production workshops have been reconstructed and modernized with modern equipment manufactured in China, Poland, Turkey.

The products of OOOSP "Siyob Sakhovati" are made from environmentally friendly, natural vegetables and fruits, exported and sold in countries near and far abroad.

The main goal of LLC JV "Siyob Sakhovati" is to make a profit. The activities of the society are also aimed at creating additional jobs, including those with reduced ability to work, reducing unemployment, developing the social infrastructure of the city and the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Certain types of activities, the list of which is determined by law, can be carried out by the company only on the basis of a special permit. If the conditions for granting a special permit to carry out a certain type of activity provide for the requirement to carry out such activity as exclusive, the company, during the period of validity of the special permit (license), has the right to carry out only the types of activities provided for by the special permit and related activities.

The average number of personnel is 159 people. Of these, 123 employees are employed in the main production, 36 people are involved in the sale of finished products. During the season, the number of employees increases to 300 people.

Currently, the production produces more than 13 types of products.

The main activities of the enterprise ООО СП "Siyob Sakhovati":

Production of various juices and concentrates, procurement and export of natural and dried agricultural products, provide jobs for the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan, provide the population with various goods and fully satisfy their needs, Produce products for export and ensure the inflow of foreign currency, as well as profit from entrepreneurial activity.

The main activity of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI" is the processing of vegetables and fruits to produce juices.

In addition, the company is engaged in the procurement and sale of agricultural products.

The company's products are sold in the domestic and foreign markets. However, the main consumer is foreign enterprises.

The product range is expressed by the following products:

Refined sunflower oil, dezorirovanoe.1-s 1 l

Refined sunflower oil, dezorirovanoe.1-s 2 l

Sunflower oil refined, dezorirovanoe.1-s / 5 l;

Cotton oil refined, dezorirovanoe.1-s / 0.92 kg;

Cotton oil refined, dezorirovanoe.1-s / 3.2 kg;

Tomato paste 30%;

Apple juice concentrate clarified 70%;

Margarine 62%;

Margarine 72%;

Margarine 82%;

Confectionery fats;

Eastern fats;

Fats of chocolate products;

RESULTS

For 9 months of 2021, the enterprise produced 1237.8 tons of tomato paste 36%, 6891 tons of apple concentrated juice 70%, harvested 892 tons of dried fruits, 139.5 tons of capers, packaged 2042 tons of vegetable oil and 2668 tons of margarine.

2980 tons of tomatoes, 7044 tons of apples and 299.7 tons of capers were accepted for processing.

The foreign trade turnover of the enterprise amounted to 3098.1 thousand US dollars, including exports - 2232.3 thousand US dollars, and imports - 865.8 thousand US dollars. In the structure of exports, canned products (juices and capers) amount to 333.3 thousand US dollars, and dried fruits - 1899.0 thousand US dollars.

Imports include spare parts in the amount of 147.9 thousand US dollars, raw materials and materials - 400.7 thousand US dollars, tires and medicines - 317.2 thousand US dollars.

For the period from February to April 2022, LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI" sold the following types of products to consumers:

Table 2. Sales of products of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI" to domestic consumers in February - April 2022

Name of product	Quantity, tons
Fats in chocolate products	25
Sunflower oil. raf, dez.1-c 2 l	221
Confectionery fats	151
Eastern fats	91
Margarine 72%	45
Margarine 82%	152
Margarine 62%	45

Tomato paste 30%	132
Cottonseed oil raff, dez.1-s/0.92kg	183
Cotton raf oil, dez.1-s/3.2kg	492
Sunflower oil raff, dez.1-c / 1 l	115
Sunflower oil raff, dez.1-s /5 l	165

Table 3. Sales of products of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI" to domestic consumers by regions for February - April 2022

City	Name of product	Quantity, tons
Samarkand	Margarine 82%	40
	Fats in chocolate products	25
	Raf cottonseed oil, dez.1-s/0.92kg/	80
	Sunflower oil, dez.1-s 2 l	76
	Sunflower oil, dez.1-c 5 l	65
	Confectionery fats	thirty
Tashkent	Sunflower oil, dez.1-s 1 l	60
	Sunflower oil, dez.1-s 2 l	75
	Sunflower oil, dez.1-c 5 l	100
	Eastern fats	68
	Confectionery fats	77
	Margarine 62%	45
	Tomato paste 30%	80
	Margarine 82%	70
Khorezm	Raf cottonseed oil, dez.1-s/0.92kg/	35
	Tomato paste 30%	52
	Sunflower oil, dez.1-s 2 l	70
	Margarine 72%	45
Bukhara	Sunflower oil, dez.1-s 1 l	55
	Raf cottonseed oil, dez.1-s/0.92kg/	68
	Margarine 82%	42
	Confectionery fats	44
	Eastern fats	23

The financial support of activities is important for the organization of production management. To evaluate the financial instruments of marketing, an analysis of financial statements is used. For this, annual reporting form 1 is used. - the balance sheet of the enterprise and form 2 - a report on the financial results of the enterprise. The analysis of the financial condition is carried out in several stages.

Stage 1: Drawing up a comparative analytical balance sheet of the enterprise LLC JV "Siyob Sakhovati", grouping of asset items.

Table 4. Analytical grouping of balance sheet assets OOO JV "Siyob Sakhovati"

Balance asset	At the beginning of the reporting period		At the end of the reporting period		Changes	
	Thousand	%	Thousand	%	Thousand	%

	sum		sum		sum	
1. Assets	56054227	100	61317744	100	5263517	9.4
1.1. Long term assets	17414798	31.1	27410877	44.7	9996079	57.4
1.2. Current assets	38639429	68.9	33906867	55.3	-4542631	-11.8
1.2.1. Inventory	13339927	24.0	8349841	13.6	-4990086	-37.4
1.2.2. Total debtors	19036651	34.0	9951764	16.2	-9084887	-47.7
1.2.3. Cash	6072920	10.9	15605262	25.5	9532342	157.0

As can be seen from the table, during the reporting period, the total value of property or assets increased by 5263517 thousand soums or by 9.4%. At the same time, the value of long-term assets increased by 9,996,079 thousand soums or 57.4%, while the value of current assets decreased by 4,542,631 thousand soums or 11.8%.

Other elements of current assets decreased significantly: inventories by 4990086 thousand soums or by 37.4%, the company's cash increased by 9532342 thousand soums or 15 times.

In general, the changes that have taken place should be considered positive. The growth of assets strengthens the economic potential of the enterprise, increases its financial stability.

Stage 2: Compilation of a comparative analytical balance sheet of the enterprise LLC JV "Siyob Sakhovati", grouping of liability items.

Table 5. Analytical grouping of balance sheet liability items OOO JV "Siyob Sakhovati"

Balance liability	At the beginning of the reporting period		At the end of the reporting period		Changes	
	Thousand sum	%	Thousand sum	%	Thousand sum	%
1. Passive	56054227	100	61317744	100	5263517	9.4
1.1. Sources of own funds	22118860	39.5	36959181	60.3	14840321	67.1
1.2. Commitments	33935367	60.5	24358563	39.7	-9576804	28.2
1.2.1. long term duties	0	-	1804943	2.9	1804943	-
1.2.2. Current responsibility	33935367	60.5	22553620	36.8	-11381747	-1.3

The table shows that the source of the growth of assets noted above is: an increase in the indicators of its own capital, the value of which increased by 14,840,321 thousand soums or 67.1% over the year, as well as a decrease in obligatory funds by 9,576,804 thousand soums or 28.2 %.

It is customary to assess the financial stability of enterprises on the basis of a number of indicators. These include:

- financial autonomy of the enterprise;
- financial stability of the enterprise;
- financial flexibility of the enterprise;
- security of the enterprise with its own working capital;
- rationality of the structure of enterprise funds;
- financial strength of the enterprise.

These indicators are universal for various enterprises (large and small, having their own production and not having it). Therefore, these indicators are defined as relative using the appropriate coefficients.

Their comparison, according to the data for the reporting and previous years, shows their dynamics and trends in the economic development of the enterprise, its financial condition.

Stage 3: Drawing up a table of indicators of economic activity of OOOSP "Siyob Sakhovati"

Table 6. Main indicators of economic activity of OOO SP "Siyob Sakhovati"

Indicators	For the same period of the previous year, thousand soums	For the reporting period, thousand soums	Changes for the reporting period	
			Thousand sum	%
Net proceeds from the sale of products (goods, works and services)	115163006	46810690	-68352316	2.2
Period expenses	2121297	2092418	-28879	-1.4
Profit from operating activities	12342634	13590348	1247714	10.1
Financing expenses	3236305	1999827	-1236478	-38.2
Profit before taxes	11243902	14933229	3689327	32.8
Net profit	8339099	12428266	4089167	49.0

The above table shows that the company received 1,247,714 thousand sums more from its core activities. Net profit also increased significantly by 4,089,167 thousand sums. In general, there are significant positive changes in financial activity.

DISCUSSION

The study showed that the volume of production and sales of products is constantly growing, and the range of products is expanding. At the same time, there are still many shortcomings in the organization of the assortment policy of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI", such as a rapid change in the range of export products, dependence on external partners, as well as on market conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the conducted research, we have developed recommendations for improving the assortment policy of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI", the essence of which is as follows:

1. The enterprise needs to conduct a systematic analysis of the range of products, as a result of which to determine the place of each product and each brand in the volume of production and sales. If we know how much each type of product benefits and to what extent, we can decide whether to combine or separate this type of product.
2. It is necessary to train employees of the marketing service in the specifics of marketing research of goods and the formation of an assortment of goods. Good training of employees is a guarantee of correct decisions.
3. It is necessary to develop an independent product policy to conquer certain segments of the consumer market.
4. The company needs to form a brand strategy that would increase the effectiveness of marketing activities in general.

The implementation of these proposals will increase the effectiveness of the assortment policy of LLC JV "SIYOB SAKHOVATI".

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" completed second edition, Tashkent "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2022, 416 p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Humanity, goodness and creativity are the foundations of our national idea" Tashkent "TASVIR" publishing house, 2021 y 36 p.
3. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "Our main task is to further increase the development of our country and the prosperity of our people" Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2010. 18 p.
4. Abduganiev A., Tolametova Z. Labor capacity of Uzbekistan. T.: "Labor", 1998. 96 p.
5. Under the editorship of K.K. Abdurakhmonov. - T.: Human development. Textbook. i.f.d., prof. "Science and technology", 2013.
6. Derevyagina L.N., Ivashkova N.I. Opit training marketing specialists in the system of additional professional education // Vestnik. 2001
7. Nasirov P. Abdullayeva L. Marketing is the basis of market economy. T.: "Teacher" 2008.
8. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kosimova M.S., Safarov B.J., Marketing management: Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2007. - 268 p.
9. Begmatov Sh. A. Kakhorov A.J. Scientific and methodological problems of introducing innovative marketing, "Economics and Education" magazine No. 5, September-October, 2016.
10. Musaeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing: Study guide. - "TURON PUBLISHING" Samarkand 2021.
11. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
14. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
16. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 105

17. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
18. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozikovich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
19. Azimovna M. S., Shohrukhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
20. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
22. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
24. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
25. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
26. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.